

Thermal and electrical performance evaluation of a hybrid solar system for a livestock farm in Belgium

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Abstract

On-farm energy use for livestock farming is a major contributor to CO₂ emissions. The integration of renewable energy sources (RES) is an important step to mitigate these emissions. RES4LIVE is an EU Horizon 2020 project focused on reducing fossil fuel usage in livestock farms. During the project, a hybrid solar thermal system was installed on a typical pig farm under Belgian weather conditions. This hybrid system converts solar radiation into both electrical and thermal energy. The electrical energy is directly used by the barn's feeding pumps and ventilation system, whereas the thermal energy is stored in an 800 liter buffer tank used as a heat source for a 60 kW heat pump installation. The hybrid solar system consists of 24 photovoltaic thermal (PVT) flat plate collectors installed in four groups of six panels with a total aperture area of 45.12 m². The PVT system has an installed electrical and thermal capacity of 8.4 kW_{electrical} and 28.8 kW_{thermal}. The heat transfer fluid (HTF) consists of 35 % propylene glycol and its flow in the system is dynamically controlled by a modular solar central control unit. The electrical and thermal performance parameters of the system are recorded every minute, including the temperature of the HTF, its flow rate and the incoming solar radiation. The data collected from the hybrid solar system is continuously being analyzed to evaluate thermal and electrical performance. During an average summer day of 2023, the HTF has gained a maximum temperature rise of about 30 °C relative to the ambient temperature. From July to February, the hybrid solar system generated approximately 4.5 MWh of thermal energy. During the five months from October to February, it produced around 2.3 MWh of electrical energy. In December 2023, the system recorded the lowest thermal and electrical energy production, corresponding with the month's lowest solar insolation. The analysis also showed that both thermal and electrical energy generated varied primarily based on the amount of insolation. The performance evaluation has shown the capability of such hybrid solar system to reduce carbon emissions and effectively replace fossil fuel consumption in the livestock sector in real working conditions.

Keywords: livestock, pig farm, renewable energy, hybrid solar thermal, photovoltaic thermal panels.

1. Introduction

Livestock farming represents a significant challenge in the context of climate change mitigation efforts, primarily due to its substantial carbon footprint stemming from energy consumption, waste production, and land use change (Steinfeld et al., 2006). Among various mitigation strategies, the integration of renewable energy sources (RES) into agricultural operations has garnered attention for its potential to reduce greenhouse gas emissions while ensuring sustainable production (Thornton, 2010).

The RES4LIVE project, supported by the EU's Horizon 2020 program (grant agreement nr. 101000785), exemplifies this approach by focusing on the implementation of renewable energy technologies in livestock farms to diminish reliance on fossil fuels. This initiative aligns with broader European efforts to transition towards a low-carbon economy and mitigate climate change impacts across sectors, including agriculture (European Commission, 2018). Solar energy, in particular, holds promise for on-farm energy generation due to its abundance and scalability. Solar photovoltaic (PV) systems have been increasingly adopted in agricultural settings worldwide, offering opportunities for decentralized electricity production and reduced operational costs. However, the intermittent nature of solar PV necessitates complementary technologies to ensure reliable energy supply, especially in settings with high energy demands such as livestock farming operations (Jäger-Waldau, 2007).

Hybrid solar thermal systems, which combine photovoltaic and thermal energy conversion technologies, present a compelling solution to address this challenge. By simultaneously generating electricity and heat from solar radiation, these systems offer enhanced energy yields and greater flexibility in meeting diverse on-farm energy needs. The integration of solar thermal technology in agriculture has been explored in various studies, highlighting its potential to improve energy efficiency and reduce greenhouse gas emissions in farming operations (Sakhare et al., 2022). Additionally, advancements in hybrid solar systems have demonstrated their applicability across different climatic conditions, with notable success in temperate regions such as Europe (Hussain et al., 2016).

The installation of a hybrid solar thermal system on a typical pig farm, as described in the RES4LIVE project, represents a novel application of this technology in the livestock sector. By leveraging both electrical and thermal energy outputs, the system addresses the multifaceted energy demands of modern farming practices while contributing to carbon emission reductions. The main objective of this study is to quantify the thermal and electrical performance of the hybrid solar system based on real life measured data.

2. Materials and Methods

The study is performed on a pig farm located in Melle (Flanders, Belgium). The farm is managed by ILVO, UGENT and HoGent for research and educational purposes alongside commercial production. It is a farrow-to-finish pig farm, housing around 105 sows, 600 piglets and 750 fattening pigs. The total building area is around 2,500 m². It is constructed out of concrete with polypropylene insulation panels dividing the compartments and partially slatted concrete floors above the manure pits. Heating is provided by a 60 kW gas boiler with a yearly fossil gas consumption of 220 MWh. Additionally heating is provided by heat lamps and a diesel powered heat cannon. The heating system is steered based on ambient temperature measurements at the animal compartments and on the stage of production. Table 1 shows heat demand (in terms of temperature) and the existing heating system with the respective production stage.

Table 1 Heat demand in the ILVO pig farm

Production stage	Heating demand	Heating system
New-born piglets	35 - 37 °C	Floor heating (boiler) and heat lamps
Weaned piglets	28 °C at the start and reducing to 25 °C	heating of incoming air (boiler) and floor heating (boiler)
Fattening pigs	20 - 25 °C	Gas cannon heating of incoming air
Sows	18 - 23 °C	no need for extra heating

Two modular heat pumps of 25 and 40 kW were installed to provide heating at different temperature levels. Besides, 24 PVT collectors were installed as described in Section 2.1.1.

2.1. Solar thermal system description

Figure 1 (A) shows a simplified schematic overview of the installed renewable energy technologies that makeup the solar-thermal system. The main components are 24 hybrid solar panels on the roof (Figure 1 C), a solar control system (Figure 1 B), two modular heat pumps of 30 kW each, and 800 liter thermal energy storage tank.

The heat transfer fluid is 35 % glycol solution heated up in the solar hybrid panels and stores the energy in the thermal storage tank. The two modular heat pumps – a high and a medium temperature heat pump - raise the temperature of water that will be circulating in the domestic hot water, air heaters and floor heater circuits of the pig farm. The thermal energy stored in the tank will be a source for the heat pumps with the aim to increase the COP. On the other hand electricity is not stored but either directly used or injected into the electricity grid.

2.1.1. Hybrid solar collector panels

The hybrid solar collector panels used in ILVO pig farm are Abora aH72SK panels (Abora, Zaragoza, Spain). They are flat plate PVT thermal collectors with Mono-crystalline. This model is capable of generating a peak electrical power of 350 W with a module rated efficiency of 17.8 % and 1200 W of thermal

power. The hybrid solar collector system consists of 24 collectors installed as four groups of six panels, resulting in a total aperture area of 45.12 m² on the roof of the pig farm. The PVT system has an installed electrical and thermal capacity of 8.4 kW_{electrical} and 28.8 kW_{thermal}, respectively. The PVTs are connected to an inverter (FIMER, Milano, Italy) on the farm for electricity supply directly to the farm.

2.1.2. Solar station unit and central controller description (MG)

The solar station is the main pumping system to transfer heat from the solar thermal collectors to the end user. The solar station used was designed by MG Sustainable Engineering AB (Sweden) with the goal to standardise solar stations for mid-size PVT applications such as in livestock farms. It was manufactured by KEterm AB in Sweden. The pump transfers heat from the solar field to the solar station heat exchanger; and an intermediate circuit transfers heat from the heat exchanger to the storage tank through another pump. Heat stored in the storage tank is used by the heat pumps to deliver the final heat to the farm.

The control system used is a RESOL MX solar controller with a RESOL DL2 datalogger which communicates data in real time to a server. The control algorithm was developed by MG Sustainable

engineering. The controller activates the solar circuit pump as soon as the solar collectors are hotter than the tank, or if solar irradiance is above a threshold ($>200 \text{ W/m}^2$ for 60 seconds). There are two heat flow meters; one for the heat delivered from the solar collectors to the solar station and one for the heat delivered to the tank. The pumps are not operated on variable speed and the flow rate in the solar circuit is ca. 30 l/min.

2.2. Data processing

Solar energy increases the temperature of HTF and the amount of heat transferred (Q) in kilowatts (kW) to the HTF can then be calculated using the equation given below.

$$Q = \dot{m}C_p\Delta T$$

Where $\dot{m}[\text{kg/s}]$ is the mass flow rate of the HTF, $C_p[\frac{\text{J}}{\text{kgK}}]$ is the specific heat capacity of the HTF at constant pressure, and $\Delta T [K]$ is the temperature difference between the hot and cold sides of the hybrid solar collector. Note that, the value of C_p of propylene glycol, which is the heat transfer fluid, is estimated using the weighted average method considering 65% water and 35% propylene glycol from **Table 2**.

Table 2. Physical properties of the heat transfer fluid 65 % water and 35 % propylene glycol (Murali et al., 2024).

	Water	Propylene glycol
Specific heat capacity, $C_p [\frac{\text{J}}{\text{kgK}}]$	4186	2200
Density, ρ at 25 °C $[\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}]$	1000	1110

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Solar irradiance levels

Figure 2 shows the solar irradiance data from July 2023 to February 2024 as a carpet plot. In four months July, August, September and October more than 1000 W/m^2 insolation was recorded. The maximum solar irradiance recorded was 350 W/m^2 in December 2023.

3.2. Hybrid solar system performance analysis

3.2.1. Thermal performance analysis

Figure 3 shows the daily amount of thermal energy produced by the hybrid solar system during the measurement period from August 2023 to February 2024. The solar irradiance values integrated over time for each day are also shown as blue bars in Figure 3. There were days when the daily thermal energy production was higher than 100 kWh in the months of August (early August) and September (early September). On the contrary, negligible heat generation is recorded in the months of December 2023 and January 2024. The produced thermal energy is as expected directly correlated the respective solar insolation data. Higher solar insolation corresponds with the higher thermal energy produced and conversely, low thermal energy output corresponds to low insolation. During the month of August 2023, the thermal energy production was nearly consistent, except for some days at the end of the month which were cloudy.

Figure 4 shows the monthly average amount of thermal energy produced by the hybrid solar system during the measurement period from August 2023 to February 2024 with the corresponding solar radiation. The produced thermal energy trend is correlated the respective solar radiation. The heat energy production reached its peak during the midday hours when the irradiance was highest. In the summer the days are longer and hence the thermal energy production is also longer. There are momentary dips in heat production around midday during winter, these are due to the circulation of relatively warm heat transfer fluid to the colder PVT panels.

Figure 2. Solar Irradiance levels (W/m^2) during the months of July 2023 to February 2024

Figure 3 Daily thermal energy production (red bars) and insolation (blue bars) during the months of August to December 2023 and January and February of 2024.

Figure 4 Average monthly heat energy generated (Blue) and solar radiation collected (Red) in kW during hours of a day,.

3.2.2. Electrical performance analysis

Figure 5 shows the daily amount of electrical energy produced by the hybrid solar system during the measurement period from October 2023 to February 2024. There were days when the daily electrical energy production was not recorded as the integrated system was on performance tests. Likewise the heat energy production the electrical energy production of the hybrid solar system is in varying relation to the solar insolation.

Figure 5 Daily electrical energy production (green bars) and insolation (blue bars) during the months of October 2023 and February of 2024

3.2.3. Electrical and thermal performance combined

Table 3 summarizes amount of average thermal and electrical energy produced by the hybrid solar system during the measurement period from August 2023 to February 2024 per day. During the seven consecutive months around 4.5 MWh thermal energy was generated by the hybrid solar system. In the five consecutive months from October to February around 2.3 MWh electrical energy was produced by the installed hybrid solar system. The month of December 2023 has days with the lowest thermal and electrical energy production that corresponds with its lowest solar isolation.

Table 3 Daily average thermal and electrical energy generated in each of the measurement months with respect to the solar isolation.

Month	Daily average Thermal energy generated [kWh]	Daily average Electrical energy generated [kWh]	Daily average Insolation [kWh]
August	51	-	465
September	52	-	434
October	16	25	213
November	6	14	82
December	0	7	44
January	10	14	87
February	13	19	115

4. Conclusions

A hybrid solar system comprising 24 collectors was installed at the ILVO pig farm. The system is being monitored based on the temperature and flow rate of the heat transfer fluid (HTF), as well as radiation and ambient temperature. Commissioned in mid-July 2023, the system's performance has been analysed over the following seven months.

From July to February, the hybrid solar system generated approximately 4.5 MWh of thermal energy. During the five months from October to February, it produced around 2.3 MWh of electrical energy. In December 2023, the system recorded the lowest thermal and electrical energy production, corresponding with the month's lowest solar insolation. The analysis also showed that both thermal and electrical energy generated varied primarily based on the amount of insolation. The performance evaluation has shown the capability of such hybrid solar system to reduce carbon emissions and effectively replace fossil fuel consumption in the livestock sector in real working conditions.

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